

Two-Sample Test Report

Page/Date/Time 1 1.3.2024 9:28:22
 Database S:\Vyzkum\Chromed\publikace ... i moč netěhotné a těhotné.S0

Descriptive Statistics Section

Variable	Count	Mean	Standard Deviation	Standard Error	95,0% LCL of Mean	95,0% UCL of Mean
netěhotné_neo	42	167,2095	57,79525	8,918001	149,1992	185,2198
X1trim_zrdavé_neoxx	73	248,1233	81,51414	9,540507	229,1046	267,1419

Note: T-alpha (netěhotné_neo) = 2,0195, T-alpha (X1trim_zrdavé_neoxx) = 1,9935

Confidence-Limits of Difference Section

Variance Assumption	DF	Mean Difference	Standard Deviation	Standard Error	95,0% LCL Difference	95,0% UCL Difference
Equal	113	-80,91376	73,79473	14,29184	-109,2285	-52,59905
Unequal	108,00	-80,91376	99,9242	13,05956	-106,8001	-55,02745

Note: T-alpha (Equal) = 1,9812, T-alpha (Unequal) = 1,9822

Equal-Variance T-Test Section

Alternative Hypothesis	T-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Power (Alpha=.050)	Power (Alpha=.010)
Difference <> 0	-5,6615	0,000000	Yes	0,999870	0,998658
Difference < 0	-5,6615	0,000000	Yes	0,999966	0,999456
Difference > 0	-5,6615	1,000000	No	0,000000	0,000000

Difference: (netěhotné_neo)-(X1trim_zrdavé_neoxx)

Aspin-Welch Unequal-Variance Test Section

Alternative Hypothesis	T-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Power (Alpha=.050)	Power (Alpha=.010)
Difference <> 0	-6,1958	0,000000	Yes	0,999985	0,999787
Difference < 0	-6,1958	0,000000	Yes	0,999997	0,999925
Difference > 0	-6,1958	1,000000	No	0,000000	0,000000

Difference: (netěhotné_neo)-(X1trim_zrdavé_neoxx)

Tests of Assumptions Section

Assumption	Value	Probability	Decision(.050)
Skewness Normality (netěhotné_neo)	0,9935	0,320454	Cannot reject normality
Kurtosis Normality (netěhotné_neo)	0,6831	0,494531	Cannot reject normality
Omnibus Normality (netěhotné_neo)	1,4537	0,483418	Cannot reject normality
Skewness Normality (X1trim_zrdavé_neoxx)	3,6300	0,000283	Reject normality
Kurtosis Normality (X1trim_zrdavé_neoxx)	2,8615	0,004216	Reject normality
Omnibus Normality (X1trim_zrdavé_neoxx)	21,3655	0,000023	Reject normality
Variance-Ratio Equal-Variance Test	1,9892	0,018568	Reject equal variances
Modified-Levene Equal-Variance Test	3,2341	0,074790	Cannot reject equal variances

Two-Sample Test Report

Page/Date/Time 2 1.3.2024 9:28:22
 Database S:\Vyzkum\Chromed\publikace ... i moč netěhotné a těhotné.S0

Median Statistics

Variable	Count	Median	95,0% LCL of Median	95,0% UCL of Median
netěhotné_neo	42	164	147	182
X1trim_zrdavé_neoxx	73	237	215	260

Mann-Whitney U or Wilcoxon Rank-Sum Test for Difference in Medians

Variable	Mann Whitney U	W Sum Ranks	Mean of W	Std Dev of W
netěhotné_neo	619	1522	2436	172,1488
X1trim_zrdavé_neoxx	2447	5148	4234	172,1488

Number Sets of Ties = 12, Multiplicity Factor = 144

Alternative Hypothesis	Exact Probability		Approximation Without Correction		Approximation With Correction			
	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Z-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Z-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050
Diff<>0			-5,3094	0,000000	Yes	-5,3065	0,000000	Yes
Diff<0			-5,3094	0,000000	Yes	-5,3065	0,000000	Yes
Diff>0			-5,3094	1,000000	No	-5,3123	1,000000	No

Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test For Different Distributions

Alternative Hypothesis	Dmn Criterion Value	Reject H0 if Greater Than	Test Alpha Level	Reject H0 (Test Alpha)	Prob Level
D(1)<>D(2)	0,471298	0,2634	.050	Yes	0,0000
D(1)<D(2)	0,471298	0,2634	.025	Yes	
D(1)>D(2)	0,000000	0,2634	.025	No	

Plots Section

Two-Sample Test Report

Page/Date/Time 3 1.3.2024 9:28:22
 Database S:\Vyzkum\Chromed\publikace ... i moč netěhotné a těhotné.S0

Two-Sample Test Report

Page/Date/Time 1 1.3.2024 9:29:10
 Database S:\Vyzkum\Chromed\publikace ... i moč netěhotné a těhotné.S0

Descriptive Statistics Section

Variable	Count	Mean	Standard Deviation	Standard Error	95,0% LCL of Mean	95,0% UCL of Mean
netěhotné_neo	42	167,2095	57,79525	8,918001	149,1992	185,2198
X2trim_zrdavé_neox	64	281,0938	82,59227	10,32403	260,4628	301,7247

Note: T-alpha (netěhotné_neo) = 2,0195, T-alpha (X2trim_zrdavé_neox) = 1,9983

Confidence-Limits of Difference Section

Variance Assumption	DF	Mean Difference	Standard Deviation	Standard Error	95,0% LCL Difference	95,0% UCL Difference
Equal	104	-113,8842	73,81796	14,65886	-142,9533	-84,81515
Unequal	103,53	-113,8842	100,8056	13,64245	-140,9392	-86,82928

Note: T-alpha (Equal) = 1,9830, T-alpha (Unequal) = 1,9831

Equal-Variance T-Test Section

Alternative Hypothesis	T-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Power (Alpha=.050)	Power (Alpha=.010)
Difference <> 0	-7,7690	0,000000	Yes	1,000000	1,000000
Difference < 0	-7,7690	0,000000	Yes	1,000000	1,000000
Difference > 0	-7,7690	1,000000	No	0,000000	0,000000

Difference: (netěhotné_neo)-(X2trim_zrdavé_neox)

Aspin-Welch Unequal-Variance Test Section

Alternative Hypothesis	T-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Power (Alpha=.050)	Power (Alpha=.010)
Difference <> 0	-8,3478	0,000000	Yes	1,000000	1,000000
Difference < 0	-8,3478	0,000000	Yes	1,000000	1,000000
Difference > 0	-8,3478	1,000000	No	0,000000	0,000000

Difference: (netěhotné_neo)-(X2trim_zrdavé_neox)

Tests of Assumptions Section

Assumption	Value	Probability	Decision(.050)
Skewness Normality (netěhotné_neo)	0,9935	0,320454	Cannot reject normality
Kurtosis Normality (netěhotné_neo)	0,6831	0,494531	Cannot reject normality
Omnibus Normality (netěhotné_neo)	1,4537	0,483418	Cannot reject normality
Skewness Normality (X2trim_zrdavé_neox)	2,4271	0,015218	Reject normality
Kurtosis Normality (X2trim_zrdavé_neox)	1,1114	0,266390	Cannot reject normality
Omnibus Normality (X2trim_zrdavé_neox)	7,1262	0,028350	Reject normality
Variance-Ratio Equal-Variance Test	2,0422	0,016394	Reject equal variances
Modified-Levene Equal-Variance Test	6,2501	0,013981	Reject equal variances

Two-Sample Test Report

Page/Date/Time 2 1.3.2024 9:29:10
 Database S:\Vyzkum\Chromed\publikace ... i moč netěhotné a těhotné.S0

Median Statistics

Variable	Count	Median	95,0% LCL of Median	95,0% UCL of Median
netěhotné_neo	42	164	147	182
X2trim_zrdavé_neox	64	263,5	234	303

Mann-Whitney U or Wilcoxon Rank-Sum Test for Difference in Medians

Variable	Mann Whitney U	W Sum Ranks	Mean of W	Std Dev of W
netěhotné_neo	320,5	1223,5	2247	154,8109
X2trim_zrdavé_neox	2367,5	4447,5	3424	154,8109

Number Sets of Ties = 13, Multiplicity Factor = 78

Alternative Hypothesis	Exact Probability		Approximation Without Correction		Approximation With Correction			
	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Z-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Z-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050
Diff<>0			-6,6113	0,000000	Yes	-6,6081	0,000000	Yes
Diff<0			-6,6113	0,000000	Yes	-6,6081	0,000000	Yes
Diff>0			-6,6113	1,000000	No	-6,6145	1,000000	No

Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test For Different Distributions

Alternative Hypothesis	Dmn Criterion Value	Reject H0 if Greater Than	Test Alpha Level	Reject H0 (Test Alpha)	Prob Level
D(1)<>D(2)	0,612351	0,2701	.050	Yes	0,0000
D(1)<D(2)	0,612351	0,2701	.025	Yes	
D(1)>D(2)	0,000000	0,2701	.025	No	

Plots Section

Two-Sample Test Report

Page/Date/Time 3 1.3.2024 9:29:10
 Database S:\Vyzkum\Chromed\publikace ... i moč netěhotné a těhotné.S0

Two-Sample Test Report

Page/Date/Time 1 1.3.2024 9:29:39
 Database S:\Vyzkum\Chromed\publikace ... i moč netěhotné a těhotné.S0

Descriptive Statistics Section

Variable	Count	Mean	Standard Deviation	Standard Error	95,0% LCL of Mean	95,0% UCL of Mean
netěhotné_neo	42	167,2095	57,79525	8,918001	149,1992	185,2198
X3trim_zrdavé_neo	62	353,1129	84,27494	10,70293	331,7111	374,5147

Note: T-alpha (netěhotné_neo) = 2,0195, T-alpha (X3trim_zrdavé_neo) = 1,9996

Confidence-Limits of Difference Section

Variance Assumption	DF	Mean Difference	Standard Deviation	Standard Error	95,0% LCL Difference	95,0% UCL Difference
Equal	102	-185,9034	74,76697	14,9419	-215,5406	-156,2662
Unequal	101,97	-185,9034	102,1888	13,93138	-213,5363	-158,2705

Note: T-alpha (Equal) = 1,9835, T-alpha (Unequal) = 1,9835

Equal-Variance T-Test Section

Alternative Hypothesis	T-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Power (Alpha=.050)	Power (Alpha=.010)
Difference <> 0	-12,4417	0,000000	Yes	1,000000	1,000000
Difference < 0	-12,4417	0,000000	Yes	1,000000	1,000000
Difference > 0	-12,4417	1,000000	No	0,000000	0,000000

Difference: (netěhotné_neo)-(X3trim_zrdavé_neo)

Aspin-Welch Unequal-Variance Test Section

Alternative Hypothesis	T-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Power (Alpha=.050)	Power (Alpha=.010)
Difference <> 0	-13,3442	0,000000	Yes	1,000000	1,000000
Difference < 0	-13,3442	0,000000	Yes	1,000000	1,000000
Difference > 0	-13,3442	1,000000	No	0,000000	0,000000

Difference: (netěhotné_neo)-(X3trim_zrdavé_neo)

Tests of Assumptions Section

Assumption	Value	Probability	Decision(.050)
Skewness Normality (netěhotné_neo)	0,9935	0,320454	Cannot reject normality
Kurtosis Normality (netěhotné_neo)	0,6831	0,494531	Cannot reject normality
Omnibus Normality (netěhotné_neo)	1,4537	0,483418	Cannot reject normality
Skewness Normality (X3trim_zrdavé_neo)	1,7515	0,079861	Cannot reject normality
Kurtosis Normality (X3trim_zrdavé_neo)	1,7689	0,076914	Cannot reject normality
Omnibus Normality (X3trim_zrdavé_neo)	6,1967	0,045124	Reject normality
Variance-Ratio Equal-Variance Test	2,1262	0,011737	Reject equal variances
Modified-Levene Equal-Variance Test	4,1563	0,044066	Reject equal variances

Two-Sample Test Report

Page/Date/Time 2 1.3.2024 9:29:39
 Database S:\Vyzkum\Chromed\publikace ... i moč netěhotné a těhotné.S0

Median Statistics

Variable	Count	Median	95,0% LCL of Median	95,0% UCL of Median
netěhotné_neo	42	164	147	182
X3trim_zrdavé_neo	62	353	329	382

Mann-Whitney U or Wilcoxon Rank-Sum Test for Difference in Medians

Variable	Mann Whitney U	W Sum Ranks	Mean of W	Std Dev of W
netěhotné_neo	75	978	2205	150,9446
X3trim_zrdavé_neo	2529	4482	3255	150,9446

Number Sets of Ties = 6, Multiplicity Factor = 36

Alternative Hypothesis	Exact Probability		Approximation Without Correction		Approximation With Correction			
	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Z-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Z-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050
Diff<>0			-8,1288	0,000000	Yes	-8,1255	0,000000	Yes
Diff<0			-8,1288	0,000000	Yes	-8,1255	0,000000	Yes
Diff>0			-8,1288	1,000000	No	-8,1321	1,000000	No

Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test For Different Distributions

Alternative Hypothesis	Dmn Criterion Value	Reject H0 if Greater Than	Test Alpha Level	Reject H0 (Test Alpha)	Prob Level
D(1)<>D(2)	0,864055	0,2718	.050	Yes	0,0000
D(1)<D(2)	0,864055	0,2718	.025	Yes	
D(1)>D(2)	0,000000	0,2718	.025	No	

Plots Section

Two-Sample Test Report

Page/Date/Time 3 1.3.2024 9:29:39
 Database S:\Vyzkum\Chromed\publikace ... i moč netěhotné a těhotné.S0

Two-Sample Test Report

Page/Date/Time 1 1.3.2024 9:44:35
 Database S:\Vyzkum\Chromed\publikace ... i moč netěhotné a těhotné.S0

Descriptive Statistics Section

Variable	Count	Mean	Standard Deviation	Standard Error	95,0% LCL of Mean	95,0% UCL of Mean
netěhotné_kyn	42	0,3385714	0,3863561	5,961605E-02	0,2181744	0,4589685
X1trim_zrdavé_kynxx	72	0,6458333	0,3562471	4,198412E-02	0,5621194	0,7295473

Note: T-alpha (netěhotné_kyn) = 2,0195, T-alpha (X1trim_zrdavé_kynxx) = 1,9939

Confidence-Limits of Difference Section

Variance Assumption	DF	Mean Difference	Standard Deviation	Standard Error	95,0% LCL Difference	95,0% UCL Difference
Equal	112	-0,3072619	0,3675554	7,136486E-02	-0,4486622	-0,1658616
Unequal	80,34	-0,3072619	0,5255312	7,291598E-02	-0,4523599	-0,162164

Note: T-alpha (Equal) = 1,9814, T-alpha (Unequal) = 1,9899

Equal-Variance T-Test Section

Alternative Hypothesis	T-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Power (Alpha=.050)	Power (Alpha=.010)
Difference <> 0	-4,3055	0,000036	Yes	0,989510	0,952096
Difference < 0	-4,3055	0,000018	Yes	0,995786	0,972997
Difference > 0	-4,3055	0,999982	No	0,000000	0,000000

Difference: (netěhotné_kyn)-(X1trim_zrdavé_kynxx)

Aspin-Welch Unequal-Variance Test Section

Alternative Hypothesis	T-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Power (Alpha=.050)	Power (Alpha=.010)
Difference <> 0	-4,2139	0,000065	Yes	0,986205	0,939479
Difference < 0	-4,2139	0,000033	Yes	0,994349	0,965313
Difference > 0	-4,2139	0,999967	No	0,000000	0,000000

Difference: (netěhotné_kyn)-(X1trim_zrdavé_kynxx)

Tests of Assumptions Section

Assumption	Value	Probability	Decision(.050)
Skewness Normality (netěhotné_kyn)	6,6085	0,000000	Reject normality
Kurtosis Normality (netěhotné_kyn)	5,4568	0,000000	Reject normality
Omnibus Normality (netěhotné_kyn)	73,4494	0,000000	Reject normality
Skewness Normality (X1trim_zrdavé_kynxx)	3,0565	0,002239	Reject normality
Kurtosis Normality (X1trim_zrdavé_kynxx)	0,3776	0,705694	Cannot reject normality
Omnibus Normality (X1trim_zrdavé_kynxx)	9,4851	0,008716	Reject normality
Variance-Ratio Equal-Variance Test	1,1762	0,541164	Cannot reject equal variances
Modified-Levene Equal-Variance Test	2,0695	0,153062	Cannot reject equal variances

Two-Sample Test Report

Page/Date/Time 2 1.3.2024 9:44:35
 Database S:\Vyzkum\Chromed\publikace ... i moč netěhotné a těhotné.S0

Median Statistics

Variable	Count	Median	95,0% LCL of Median	95,0% UCL of Median
netěhotné_kyn	42	0,245	0,17	0,35
X1trim_zrdavé_kynxx	72	0,535	0,45	0,63

Mann-Whitney U or Wilcoxon Rank-Sum Test for Difference in Medians

Variable	Mann Whitney U	W Sum Ranks	Mean of W	Std Dev of W
netěhotné_kyn	568,5	1471,5	2415	170,2076
X1trim_zrdavé_kynxx	2455,5	5083,5	4140	170,2076

Number Sets of Ties = 28, Multiplicity Factor = 480

Alternative Hypothesis	Exact Probability		Approximation Without Correction		Approximation With Correction			
	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Z-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Z-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050
Diff<>0			-5,5432	0,000000	Yes	-5,5403	0,000000	Yes
Diff<0			-5,5432	0,000000	Yes	-5,5403	0,000000	Yes
Diff>0			-5,5432	1,000000	No	-5,5462	1,000000	No

Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test For Different Distributions

Alternative Hypothesis	Dmn Criterion Value	Reject H0 if Greater Than	Test Alpha Level	Reject H0 (Test Alpha)	Prob Level
D(1)<>D(2)	0,492063	0,2641	.050	Yes	0,0000
D(1)<D(2)	0,492063	0,2641	.025	Yes	
D(1)>D(2)	0,023810	0,2641	.025	No	

Plots Section

Two-Sample Test Report

Page/Date/Time 3 1.3.2024 9:44:35
 Database S:\Vyzkum\Chromed\publikace ... i moč netěhotné a těhotné.S0

Two-Sample Test Report

Page/Date/Time 1 1.3.2024 9:44:57
 Database S:\Vyzkum\Chromed\publikace ... i moč netěhotné a těhotné.S0

Descriptive Statistics Section

Variable	Count	Mean	Standard Deviation	Standard Error	95,0% LCL of Mean	95,0% UCL of Mean
netěhotné_kyn	42	0,3385714	0,3863561	5,961605E-02	0,2181744	0,4589685
X2trim_zrdavé_kynx	62	0,9130645	0,4820196	6,121655E-02	0,7906545	1,035475

Note: T-alpha (netěhotné_kyn) = 2,0195, T-alpha (X2trim_zrdavé_kynx) = 1,9996

Confidence-Limits of Difference Section

Variance Assumption	DF	Mean Difference	Standard Deviation	Standard Error	95,0% LCL Difference	95,0% UCL Difference
Equal	102	-0,5744931	0,4460396	8,913937E-02	-0,7513006	-0,3976856
Unequal	99,04	-0,5744931	0,6177492	8,544905E-02	-0,7440417	-0,4049444

Note: T-alpha (Equal) = 1,9835, T-alpha (Unequal) = 1,9842

Equal-Variance T-Test Section

Alternative Hypothesis	T-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Power (Alpha=.050)	Power (Alpha=.010)
Difference <> 0	-6,4449	0,000000	Yes	0,999995	0,999916
Difference < 0	-6,4449	0,000000	Yes	0,999999	0,999972
Difference > 0	-6,4449	1,000000	No	0,000000	0,000000

Difference: (netěhotné_kyn)-(X2trim_zrdavé_kynx)

Aspin-Welch Unequal-Variance Test Section

Alternative Hypothesis	T-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Power (Alpha=.050)	Power (Alpha=.010)
Difference <> 0	-6,7232	0,000000	Yes	0,999999	0,999972
Difference < 0	-6,7232	0,000000	Yes	1,000000	0,999992
Difference > 0	-6,7232	1,000000	No	0,000000	0,000000

Difference: (netěhotné_kyn)-(X2trim_zrdavé_kynx)

Tests of Assumptions Section

Assumption	Value	Probability	Decision(.050)
Skewness Normality (netěhotné_kyn)	6,6085	0,000000	Reject normality
Kurtosis Normality (netěhotné_kyn)	5,4568	0,000000	Reject normality
Omnibus Normality (netěhotné_kyn)	73,4494	0,000000	Reject normality
Skewness Normality (X2trim_zrdavé_kynx)	3,3806	0,000723	Reject normality
Kurtosis Normality (X2trim_zrdavé_kynx)	1,4281	0,153252	Cannot reject normality
Omnibus Normality (X2trim_zrdavé_kynx)	13,4677	0,001190	Reject normality
Variance-Ratio Equal-Variance Test	1,5565	0,134861	Cannot reject equal variances
Modified-Levene Equal-Variance Test	5,4723	0,021269	Reject equal variances

Two-Sample Test Report

Page/Date/Time 2 1.3.2024 9:44:57
 Database S:\Vyzkum\Chromed\publikace ... i moč netěhotné a těhotné.S0

Median Statistics

Variable	Count	Median	95,0% LCL of Median	95,0% UCL of Median
netěhotné_kyn	42	0,245	0,17	0,35
X2trim_zrdavé_kynx	62	0,8	0,67	0,97

Mann-Whitney U or Wilcoxon Rank-Sum Test for Difference in Medians

Variable	Mann Whitney U	W Sum Ranks	Mean of W	Std Dev of W
netěhotné_kyn	226	1129	2205	150,9317
X2trim_zrdavé_kynx	2378	4331	3255	150,9317

Number Sets of Ties = 23, Multiplicity Factor = 228

Alternative Hypothesis	Exact Probability		Approximation Without Correction		Approximation With Correction			
	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Z-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Z-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050
Diff<>0			-7,1291	0,000000	Yes	-7,1257	0,000000	Yes
Diff<0			-7,1291	0,000000	Yes	-7,1257	0,000000	Yes
Diff>0			-7,1291	1,000000	No	-7,1324	1,000000	No

Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test For Different Distributions

Alternative Hypothesis	Dmn Criterion Value	Reject H0 if Greater Than	Test Alpha Level	Reject H0 (Test Alpha)	Prob Level
D(1)<>D(2)	0,703533	0,2718	.050	Yes	0,0000
D(1)<D(2)	0,703533	0,2718	.025	Yes	
D(1)>D(2)	0,023810	0,2718	.025	No	

Plots Section

Two-Sample Test Report

Page/Date/Time 3 1.3.2024 9:44:57
 Database S:\Vyzkum\Chromed\publikace ... i moč netěhotné a těhotné.S0

Two-Sample Test Report

Page/Date/Time 1 1.3.2024 9:45:18
 Database S:\Vyzkum\Chromed\publikace ... i moč netěhotné a těhotné.S0

Descriptive Statistics Section

Variable	Count	Mean	Standard Deviation	Standard Error	95,0% LCL of Mean	95,0% UCL of Mean
netěhotné_kyn	42	0,3385714	0,3863561	5,961605E-02	0,2181744	0,4589685
X3trim_zrdavé_kyn	62	1,365	0,644741	8,188219E-02	1,201266	1,528734

Note: T-alpha (netěhotné_kyn) = 2,0195, T-alpha (X3trim_zrdavé_kyn) = 1,9996

Confidence-Limits of Difference Section

Variance Assumption	DF	Mean Difference	Standard Deviation	Standard Error	95,0% LCL Difference	95,0% UCL Difference
Equal	102	-1,026429	0,5555183	0,1110183	-1,246633	-0,8062243
Unequal	100,71	-1,026429	0,7516396	0,1012856	-1,227359	-0,8254982

Note: T-alpha (Equal) = 1,9835, T-alpha (Unequal) = 1,9838

Equal-Variance T-Test Section

Alternative Hypothesis	T-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Power (Alpha=.050)	Power (Alpha=.010)
Difference <> 0	-9,2456	0,000000	Yes	1,000000	1,000000
Difference < 0	-9,2456	0,000000	Yes	1,000000	1,000000
Difference > 0	-9,2456	1,000000	No	0,000000	0,000000

Difference: (netěhotné_kyn)-(X3trim_zrdavé_kyn)

Aspin-Welch Unequal-Variance Test Section

Alternative Hypothesis	T-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Power (Alpha=.050)	Power (Alpha=.010)
Difference <> 0	-10,1340	0,000000	Yes	1,000000	1,000000
Difference < 0	-10,1340	0,000000	Yes	1,000000	1,000000
Difference > 0	-10,1340	1,000000	No	0,000000	0,000000

Difference: (netěhotné_kyn)-(X3trim_zrdavé_kyn)

Tests of Assumptions Section

Assumption	Value	Probability	Decision(.050)
Skewness Normality (netěhotné_kyn)	6,6085	0,000000	Reject normality
Kurtosis Normality (netěhotné_kyn)	5,4568	0,000000	Reject normality
Omnibus Normality (netěhotné_kyn)	73,4494	0,000000	Reject normality
Skewness Normality (X3trim_zrdavé_kyn)	3,2455	0,001172	Reject normality
Kurtosis Normality (X3trim_zrdavé_kyn)	2,0760	0,037892	Reject normality
Omnibus Normality (X3trim_zrdavé_kyn)	14,8433	0,000598	Reject normality
Variance-Ratio Equal-Variance Test	2,7848	0,000747	Reject equal variances
Modified-Levene Equal-Variance Test	13,9225	0,000314	Reject equal variances

Two-Sample Test Report

Page/Date/Time 2 1.3.2024 9:45:18
 Database S:\Vyzkum\Chromed\publikace ... i moč netěhotné a těhotné.S0

Median Statistics

Variable	Count	Median	95,0% LCL of Median	95,0% UCL of Median
netěhotné_kyn	42	0,245	0,17	0,35
X3trim_zrdavé_kyn	62	1,24	1	1,5

Mann-Whitney U or Wilcoxon Rank-Sum Test for Difference in Medians

Variable	Mann Whitney U	W Sum Ranks	Mean of W	Std Dev of W
netěhotné_kyn	104	1007	2205	150,9345
X3trim_zrdavé_kyn	2500	4453	3255	150,9345

Number Sets of Ties = 19, Multiplicity Factor = 186

Alternative Hypothesis	Exact Probability		Approximation Without Correction		Approximation With Correction			
	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Z-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Z-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050
Diff<>0			-7,9372	0,000000	Yes	-7,9339	0,000000	Yes
Diff<0			-7,9372	0,000000	Yes	-7,9339	0,000000	Yes
Diff>0			-7,9372	1,000000	No	-7,9405	1,000000	No

Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test For Different Distributions

Alternative Hypothesis	Dmn Criterion Value	Reject H0 if Greater Than	Test Alpha Level	Reject H0 (Test Alpha)	Prob Level
D(1)<>D(2)	0,863287	0,2718	.050	Yes	0,0000
D(1)<D(2)	0,863287	0,2718	.025	Yes	
D(1)>D(2)	0,000000	0,2718	.025	No	

Plots Section

Two-Sample Test Report

Page/Date/Time 3 1.3.2024 9:45:18
 Database S:\Vyzkum\Chromed\publikace ... i moč netěhotné a těhotné.S0

Two-Sample Test Report

Page/Date/Time 1 1.3.2024 9:45:40
 Database S:\Vyzkum\Chromed\publikace ... i moč netěhotné a těhotné.S0

Descriptive Statistics Section

Variable	Count	Mean	Standard Deviation	Standard Error	95,0% LCL of Mean	95,0% UCL of Mean
netěhotné_trp	42	5,289762	2,644817	0,4081041	4,465579	6,113945
X1trim_zrdavé_TRPxx	73	11,50863	4,081313	0,4776815	10,55639	12,46087

Note: T-alpha (netěhotné_trp) = 2,0195, T-alpha (X1trim_zrdavé_TRPxx) = 1,9935

Confidence-Limits of Difference Section

Variance Assumption	DF	Mean Difference	Standard Deviation	Standard Error	95,0% LCL Difference	95,0% UCL Difference
Equal	113	-6,218868	3,626487	0,7023426	-7,610336	-4,827401
Unequal	111,32	-6,218868	4,86335	0,6282743	-7,463797	-4,97394

Note: T-alpha (Equal) = 1,9812, T-alpha (Unequal) = 1,9815

Equal-Variance T-Test Section

Alternative Hypothesis	T-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Power (Alpha=.050)	Power (Alpha=.010)
Difference <> 0	-8,8545	0,000000	Yes	1,000000	1,000000
Difference < 0	-8,8545	0,000000	Yes	1,000000	1,000000
Difference > 0	-8,8545	1,000000	No	0,000000	0,000000

Difference: (netěhotné_trp)-(X1trim_zrdavé_TRPxx)

Aspin-Welch Unequal-Variance Test Section

Alternative Hypothesis	T-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Power (Alpha=.050)	Power (Alpha=.010)
Difference <> 0	-9,8983	0,000000	Yes	1,000000	1,000000
Difference < 0	-9,8983	0,000000	Yes	1,000000	1,000000
Difference > 0	-9,8983	1,000000	No	0,000000	0,000000

Difference: (netěhotné_trp)-(X1trim_zrdavé_TRPxx)

Tests of Assumptions Section

Assumption	Value	Probability	Decision(.050)
Skewness Normality (netěhotné_trp)	5,3446	0,000000	Reject normality
Kurtosis Normality (netěhotné_trp)	4,7054	0,000003	Reject normality
Omnibus Normality (netěhotné_trp)	50,7049	0,000000	Reject normality
Skewness Normality (X1trim_zrdavé_TRPxx)	2,1747	0,029656	Reject normality
Kurtosis Normality (X1trim_zrdavé_TRPxx)	1,0318	0,302170	Cannot reject normality
Omnibus Normality (X1trim_zrdavé_TRPxx)	5,7937	0,055196	Cannot reject normality
Variance-Ratio Equal-Variance Test	2,3813	0,003285	Reject equal variances
Modified-Levene Equal-Variance Test	9,8547	0,002162	Reject equal variances

Two-Sample Test Report

Page/Date/Time 2 1.3.2024 9:45:40
 Database S:\Vyzkum\Chromed\publikace ... i moč netěhotné a těhotné.S0

Median Statistics

Variable	Count	Median	95,0% LCL of Median	95,0% UCL of Median
netěhotné_trp	42	4,995	4,2	5,72
X1trim_zrdavé_TRPxx	73	11,2	9,86	11,75

Mann-Whitney U or Wilcoxon Rank-Sum Test for Difference in Medians

Variable	Mann Whitney U	W Sum Ranks	Mean of W	Std Dev of W
netěhotné_trp	228,5	1131,5	2436	172,1555
X1trim_zrdavé_TRPxx	2837,5	5538,5	4234	172,1555

Number Sets of Ties = 4, Multiplicity Factor = 24

Alternative Hypothesis	Exact Probability		Approximation Without Correction		Approximation With Correction			
	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Z-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Z-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050
Diff<>0			-7,5774	0,000000	Yes	-7,5745	0,000000	Yes
Diff<0			-7,5774	0,000000	Yes	-7,5745	0,000000	Yes
Diff>0			-7,5774	1,000000	No	-7,5804	1,000000	No

Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test For Different Distributions

Alternative Hypothesis	Dmn Criterion Value	Reject H0 if Greater Than	Test Alpha Level	Reject H0 (Test Alpha)	Prob Level
D(1)<>D(2)	0,795173	0,2634	.050	Yes	0,0000
D(1)<D(2)	0,795173	0,2634	.025	Yes	
D(1)>D(2)	0,000000	0,2634	.025	No	

Plots Section

Two-Sample Test Report

Page/Date/Time 3 1.3.2024 9:45:40
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Two-Sample Test Report

Page/Date/Time 1 1.3.2024 9:46:03
 Database S:\Vyzkum\Chromed\publikace ... i moč netěhotné a těhotné.S0

Descriptive Statistics Section

Variable	Count	Mean	Standard Deviation	Standard Error	95,0% LCL of Mean	95,0% UCL of Mean
netěhotné_trp	42	5,289762	2,644817	0,4081041	4,465579	6,113945
X2trim_zrdavé_TRPx	64	13,305	4,732737	0,5915921	12,1228	14,4872

Note: T-alpha (netěhotné_trp) = 2,0195, T-alpha (X2trim_zrdavé_TRPx) = 1,9983

Confidence-Limits of Difference Section

Variance Assumption	DF	Mean Difference	Standard Deviation	Standard Error	95,0% LCL Difference	95,0% UCL Difference
Equal	104	-8,015238	4,040565	0,8023807	-9,606389	-6,424087
Unequal	101,80	-8,015238	5,42161	0,7187003	-9,44081	-6,589666

Note: T-alpha (Equal) = 1,9830, T-alpha (Unequal) = 1,9835

Equal-Variance T-Test Section

Alternative Hypothesis	T-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Power (Alpha=.050)	Power (Alpha=.010)
Difference <> 0	-9,9893	0,000000	Yes	1,000000	1,000000
Difference < 0	-9,9893	0,000000	Yes	1,000000	1,000000
Difference > 0	-9,9893	1,000000	No	0,000000	0,000000

Difference: (netěhotné_trp)-(X2trim_zrdavé_TRPx)

Aspin-Welch Unequal-Variance Test Section

Alternative Hypothesis	T-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Power (Alpha=.050)	Power (Alpha=.010)
Difference <> 0	-11,1524	0,000000	Yes	1,000000	1,000000
Difference < 0	-11,1524	0,000000	Yes	1,000000	1,000000
Difference > 0	-11,1524	1,000000	No	0,000000	0,000000

Difference: (netěhotné_trp)-(X2trim_zrdavé_TRPx)

Tests of Assumptions Section

Assumption	Value	Probability	Decision(.050)
Skewness Normality (netěhotné_trp)	5,3446	0,000000	Reject normality
Kurtosis Normality (netěhotné_trp)	4,7054	0,000003	Reject normality
Omnibus Normality (netěhotné_trp)	50,7049	0,000000	Reject normality
Skewness Normality (X2trim_zrdavé_TRPx)	1,8300	0,067245	Cannot reject normality
Kurtosis Normality (X2trim_zrdavé_TRPx)	0,1095	0,912778	Cannot reject normality
Omnibus Normality (X2trim_zrdavé_TRPx)	3,3610	0,186280	Cannot reject normality
Variance-Ratio Equal-Variance Test	3,2021	0,000138	Reject equal variances
Modified-Levene Equal-Variance Test	16,1716	0,000110	Reject equal variances

Two-Sample Test Report

Page/Date/Time 2 1.3.2024 9:46:03
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Median Statistics

Variable	Count	Median	95,0% LCL of Median	95,0% UCL of Median
netěhotné_trp	42	4,995	4,2	5,72
X2trim_zrdavé_TRPx	64	12,6	11,23	14,25

Mann-Whitney U or Wilcoxon Rank-Sum Test for Difference in Medians

Variable	Mann Whitney U	W Sum Ranks	Mean of W	Std Dev of W
netěhotné_trp	124	1027	2247	154,8156
X2trim_zrdavé_TRPx	2564	4644	3424	154,8156

Number Sets of Ties = 1, Multiplicity Factor = 6

Alternative Hypothesis	Exact Probability		Approximation Without Correction		Approximation With Correction			
	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Z-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Z-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050
Diff<>0			-7,8803	0,000000	Yes	-7,8771	0,000000	Yes
Diff<0			-7,8803	0,000000	Yes	-7,8771	0,000000	Yes
Diff>0			-7,8803	1,000000	No	-7,8836	1,000000	No

Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test For Different Distributions

Alternative Hypothesis	Dmn Criterion Value	Reject H0 if Greater Than	Test Alpha Level	Reject H0 (Test Alpha)	Prob Level
D(1)<>D(2)	0,835565	0,2701	.050	Yes	0,0000
D(1)<D(2)	0,835565	0,2701	.025	Yes	
D(1)>D(2)	0,000000	0,2701	.025	No	

Plots Section

Two-Sample Test Report

Page/Date/Time 3 1.3.2024 9:46:03
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Two-Sample Test Report

Page/Date/Time 1 1.3.2024 9:46:22
 Database S:\Vyzkum\Chromed\publikace ... i moč netěhotné a těhotné.S0

Descriptive Statistics Section

Variable	Count	Mean	Standard Deviation	Standard Error	95,0% LCL of Mean	95,0% UCL of Mean
netěhotné_trp	42	5,289762	2,644817	0,4081041	4,465579	6,113945
X3trim_zrdavé_TRP	62	16,71952	5,537613	0,7032775	15,31323	18,12581

Note: T-alpha (netěhotné_trp) = 2,0195, T-alpha (X3trim_zrdavé_TRP) = 1,9996

Confidence-Limits of Difference Section

Variance Assumption	DF	Mean Difference	Standard Deviation	Standard Error	95,0% LCL Difference	95,0% UCL Difference
Equal	102	-11,42975	4,598989	0,9190912	-13,25277	-9,606741
Unequal	93,26	-11,42975	6,136792	0,8131102	-13,04437	-9,815139

Note: T-alpha (Equal) = 1,9835, T-alpha (Unequal) = 1,9857

Equal-Variance T-Test Section

Alternative Hypothesis	T-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Power (Alpha=.050)	Power (Alpha=.010)
Difference <> 0	-12,4359	0,000000	Yes	1,000000	1,000000
Difference < 0	-12,4359	0,000000	Yes	1,000000	1,000000
Difference > 0	-12,4359	1,000000	No	0,000000	0,000000

Difference: (netěhotné_trp)-(X3trim_zrdavé_TRP)

Aspin-Welch Unequal-Variance Test Section

Alternative Hypothesis	T-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Power (Alpha=.050)	Power (Alpha=.010)
Difference <> 0	-14,0568	0,000000	Yes	1,000000	1,000000
Difference < 0	-14,0568	0,000000	Yes	1,000000	1,000000
Difference > 0	-14,0568	1,000000	No	0,000000	0,000000

Difference: (netěhotné_trp)-(X3trim_zrdavé_TRP)

Tests of Assumptions Section

Assumption	Value	Probability	Decision(.050)
Skewness Normality (netěhotné_trp)	5,3446	0,000000	Reject normality
Kurtosis Normality (netěhotné_trp)	4,7054	0,000003	Reject normality
Omnibus Normality (netěhotné_trp)	50,7049	0,000000	Reject normality
Skewness Normality (X3trim_zrdavé_TRP)	1,6378	0,101473	Cannot reject normality
Kurtosis Normality (X3trim_zrdavé_TRP)	0,9321	0,351288	Cannot reject normality
Omnibus Normality (X3trim_zrdavé_TRP)	3,5510	0,169396	Cannot reject normality
Variance-Ratio Equal-Variance Test	4,3838	0,000002	Reject equal variances
Modified-Levene Equal-Variance Test	16,1813	0,000111	Reject equal variances

Two-Sample Test Report

Page/Date/Time 2 1.3.2024 9:46:22
 Database S:\Vyzkum\Chromed\publikace ... i moč netěhotné a těhotné.S0

Median Statistics

Variable	Count	Median	95,0% LCL of Median	95,0% UCL of Median
netěhotné_trp	42	4,995	4,2	5,72
X3trim_zrdavé_TRP	62	16,13	14,66	17,76

Mann-Whitney U or Wilcoxon Rank-Sum Test for Difference in Medians

Variable	Mann Whitney U	W Sum Ranks	Mean of W	Std Dev of W
netěhotné_trp	77,5	980,5	2205	150,9462
X3trim_zrdavé_TRP	2526,5	4479,5	3255	150,9462

Number Sets of Ties = 2, Multiplicity Factor = 12

Alternative Hypothesis	Exact Probability		Approximation Without Correction		Approximation With Correction			
	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Z-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Z-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050
Diff<>0			-8,1122	0,000000	Yes	-8,1088	0,000000	Yes
Diff<0			-8,1122	0,000000	Yes	-8,1088	0,000000	Yes
Diff>0			-8,1122	1,000000	No	-8,1155	1,000000	No

Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test For Different Distributions

Alternative Hypothesis	Dmn Criterion Value	Reject H0 if Greater Than	Test Alpha Level	Reject H0 (Test Alpha)	Prob Level
D(1)<>D(2)	0,927803	0,2718	.050	Yes	0,0000
D(1)<D(2)	0,927803	0,2718	.025	Yes	
D(1)>D(2)	0,000000	0,2718	.025	No	

Plots Section

Two-Sample Test Report

Page/Date/Time 3 1.3.2024 9:46:22
 Database S:\Vyzkum\Chromed\publikace ... i moč netěhotné a těhotné.S0

Two-Sample Test Report

Page/Date/Time 1 1.3.2024 9:46:53
 Database S:\Vyzkum\Chromed\publikace ... i moč netěhotné a těhotné.S0

Descriptive Statistics Section

Variable	Count	Mean	Standard Deviation	Standard Error	95,0% LCL of Mean	95,0% UCL of Mean
netěhotné_kyn_trp	42	62,73024	64,33308	9,926809	42,68264	82,77784
X1trim_zrdavé_kyn__trpxx	72	61,94081	56,22917	24,30608	2,864499	50,51752

Note: T-alpha (netěhotné_kyn_trp) = 2,0195, T-alpha (X1trim_zrdavé_kyn__trpxx) = 1,9939

Confidence-Limits of Difference Section

Variance Assumption	DF	Mean Difference	Standard Deviation	Standard Error	95,0% LCL Difference	95,0% UCL Difference
Equal	112	6,501071	43,46944	8,440061	-10,22183	23,22397
Unequal	47,92	6,501071	68,77158	10,33184	-14,27338	27,27552

Note: T-alpha (Equal) = 1,9814, T-alpha (Unequal) = 2,0107

Equal-Variance T-Test Section

Alternative Hypothesis	T-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Power (Alpha=.050)	Power (Alpha=.010)
Difference <> 0	0,7703	0,442765	No	0,119020	0,035044
Difference < 0	0,7703	0,778617	No	0,007966	0,001010
Difference > 0	0,7703	0,221383	No	0,189636	0,058752

Difference: (netěhotné_kyn_trp)-(X1trim_zrdavé_kyn__trpxx)

Aspin-Welch Unequal-Variance Test Section

Alternative Hypothesis	T-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Power (Alpha=.050)	Power (Alpha=.010)
Difference <> 0	0,6292	0,532189	No	0,094581	0,025261
Difference < 0	0,6292	0,733906	No	0,011747	0,001650
Difference > 0	0,6292	0,266094	No	0,152804	0,043205

Difference: (netěhotné_kyn_trp)-(X1trim_zrdavé_kyn__trpxx)

Tests of Assumptions Section

Assumption	Value	Probability	Decision(.050)
Skewness Normality (netěhotné_kyn_trp)	7,0365	0,000000	Reject normality
Kurtosis Normality (netěhotné_kyn_trp)	5,7057	0,000000	Reject normality
Omnibus Normality (netěhotné_kyn_trp)	82,0679	0,000000	Reject normality
Skewness Normality (X1trim_zrdavé_kyn__trpxx)		4,0033	0,000062 Reject normality
Kurtosis Normality (X1trim_zrdavé_kyn__trpxx)		2,7363	0,006213 Reject normality
Omnibus Normality (X1trim_zrdavé_kyn__trpxx)		23,5138	0,000008 Reject normality
Variance-Ratio Equal-Variance Test	7,0055	0,000000	Reject equal variances
Modified-Levene Equal-Variance Test	1,8742	0,173730	Cannot reject equal variances

Two-Sample Test Report

Page/Date/Time 2 1.3.2024 9:46:53
 Database S:\Vyzkum\Chromed\publikace ... i moč netěhotné a těhotné.S0

Median Statistics

Variable	Count	Median	95,0% LCL of Median	95,0% UCL of Median
netěhotné_kyn_trp	42	52,97	43,32	62,1
X1trim_zrdavé_kyn__trpxx	72	53,755	46,52	59,76

Mann-Whitney U or Wilcoxon Rank-Sum Test for Difference in Medians

Variable	Mann Whitney U	W Sum Ranks	Mean of W	Std Dev of W
netěhotné_kyn_trp	1476	2379	2415	170,2344
X1trim_zrdavé_kyn__trpxx	1548	4176	4140	170,2344

Number Sets of Ties = 2, Multiplicity Factor = 12

Alternative Hypothesis	Exact Probability		Approximation Without Correction		Approximation With Correction			
	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Z-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Z-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050
Diff<>0			-0,2115	0,832518	No	-0,2085	0,834811	No
Diff<0			-0,2115	0,416259	No	-0,2085	0,417405	No
Diff>0			-0,2115	0,583741	No	-0,2144	0,584886	No

Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test For Different Distributions

Alternative Hypothesis	Dmn Criterion Value	Reject H0 if Greater Than	Test Alpha Level	Reject H0 (Test Alpha)	Prob Level
D(1)<>D(2)	0,111111	0,2641	.050	No	0,8583
D(1)<D(2)	0,111111	0,2641	.025	No	
D(1)>D(2)	0,087302	0,2641	.025	No	

Plots Section

Two-Sample Test Report

Page/Date/Time 3 1.3.2024 9:46:53
 Database S:\Vyzkum\Chromed\publikace ... i moč netěhotné a těhotné.S0

Two-Sample Test Report

Page/Date/Time 1 1.3.2024 9:47:10
 Database S:\Vyzkum\Chromed\publikace ... i moč netěhotné a těhotné.S0

Descriptive Statistics Section

Variable	Count	Mean	Standard Deviation	Standard Error	95,0% LCL of Mean	95,0% UCL of Mean
netěhotné_kyn_trp	42	62,73024	64,33308	9,926809	42,68264	82,77784
X2trim_zrdavé_kyn__trpx	62	76,04224	68,60758	29,27578	3,718028	61,17292

Note: T-alpha (netěhotné_kyn_trp) = 2,0195, T-alpha (X2trim_zrdavé_kyn__trpx) = 1,9996

Confidence-Limits of Difference Section

Variance Assumption	DF	Mean Difference	Standard Deviation	Standard Error	95,0% LCL Difference	95,0% UCL Difference
Equal	102	-5,877343	46,64949	9,32273	-24,36893	12,61425
Unequal	52,61	-5,877343	70,68109	10,60025	-27,14239	15,3877

Note: T-alpha (Equal) = 1,9835, T-alpha (Unequal) = 2,0061

Equal-Variance T-Test Section

Alternative Hypothesis	T-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Power (Alpha=.050)	Power (Alpha=.010)
Difference <> 0	-0,6304	0,529822	No	0,095741	0,025955
Difference < 0	-0,6304	0,264911	No	0,154197	0,044169
Difference > 0	-0,6304	0,735089	No	0,011570	0,001597

Difference: (netěhotné_kyn_trp)-(X2trim_zrdavé_kyn__trpx)

Aspin-Welch Unequal-Variance Test Section

Alternative Hypothesis	T-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Power (Alpha=.050)	Power (Alpha=.010)
Difference <> 0	-0,5545	0,581618	No	0,084585	0,021672
Difference < 0	-0,5545	0,290809	No	0,136210	0,037052
Difference > 0	-0,5545	0,709191	No	0,014181	0,002073

Difference: (netěhotné_kyn_trp)-(X2trim_zrdavé_kyn__trpx)

Tests of Assumptions Section

Assumption	Value	Probability	Decision(.050)
Skewness Normality (netěhotné_kyn_trp)	7,0365	0,000000	Reject normality
Kurtosis Normality (netěhotné_kyn_trp)	5,7057	0,000000	Reject normality
Omnibus Normality (netěhotné_kyn_trp)	82,0679	0,000000	Reject normality
Skewness Normality (X2trim_zrdavé_kyn__trpx)		3,1817	0,001464 Reject normality
Kurtosis Normality (X2trim_zrdavé_kyn__trpx)		1,2304	0,218534 Cannot reject normality
Omnibus Normality (X2trim_zrdavé_kyn__trpx)		11,6370	0,002972 Reject normality
Variance-Ratio Equal-Variance Test	4,8289	0,000000	Reject equal variances
Modified-Levene Equal-Variance Test	0,5030	0,479804	Cannot reject equal variances

Two-Sample Test Report

Page/Date/Time 2 1.3.2024 9:47:10
 Database S:\Vyzkum\Chromed\publikace ... i moč netěhotné a těhotné.S0

Median Statistics

Variable	Count	Median	95,0% LCL of Median	95,0% UCL of Median
netěhotné_kyn_trp	42	52,97	43,32	62,1
X2trim_zrdavé_kyn__trpx	62	60,55	53,69	68,36

Mann-Whitney U or Wilcoxon Rank-Sum Test for Difference in Medians

Variable	Mann Whitney U	W Sum Ranks	Mean of W	Std Dev of W
netěhotné_kyn_trp	961	1864	2205	150,9462
X2trim_zrdavé_kyn__trpx	1643	3596	3255	150,9462

Number Sets of Ties = 2, Multiplicity Factor = 12

Alternative Hypothesis	Exact Probability		Approximation Without Correction		Approximation With Correction			
	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Z-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Z-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050
Diff<>0			-2,2591	0,023878	Yes	-2,2558	0,024085	Yes
Diff<0			-2,2591	0,011939	Yes	-2,2558	0,012043	Yes
Diff>0			-2,2591	0,988061	No	-2,2624	0,988164	No

Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test For Different Distributions

Alternative Hypothesis	Dmn Criterion Value	Reject H0 if Greater Than	Test Alpha Level	Reject H0 (Test Alpha)	Prob Level
D(1)<>D(2)	0,236559	0,2718	.050	No	0,0995
D(1)<D(2)	0,236559	0,2718	.025	No	
D(1)>D(2)	0,023810	0,2718	.025	No	

Plots Section

Two-Sample Test Report

Page/Date/Time 3 1.3.2024 9:47:10
 Database S:\Vyzkum\Chromed\publikace ... i moč netěhotné a těhotné.S0

Two-Sample Test Report

Page/Date/Time 1 1.3.2024 9:47:10
 Database S:\Vyzkum\Chromed\publikace ... i moč netěhotné a těhotné.S0

Descriptive Statistics Section

Variable	Count	Mean	Standard Deviation	Standard Error	95,0% LCL of Mean	95,0% UCL of Mean
netěhotné_kyn_trp	42	62,73024	64,33308	9,926809	42,68264	82,77784
X2trim_zrdavé_kyn__trpx	62	76,04224	68,60758	29,27578	3,718028	61,17292

Note: T-alpha (netěhotné_kyn_trp) = 2,0195, T-alpha (X2trim_zrdavé_kyn__trpx) = 1,9996

Confidence-Limits of Difference Section

Variance Assumption	DF	Mean Difference	Standard Deviation	Standard Error	95,0% LCL Difference	95,0% UCL Difference
Equal	102	-5,877343	46,64949	9,32273	-24,36893	12,61425
Unequal	52,61	-5,877343	70,68109	10,60025	-27,14239	15,3877

Note: T-alpha (Equal) = 1,9835, T-alpha (Unequal) = 2,0061

Equal-Variance T-Test Section

Alternative Hypothesis	T-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Power (Alpha=.050)	Power (Alpha=.010)
Difference <> 0	-0,6304	0,529822	No	0,095741	0,025955
Difference < 0	-0,6304	0,264911	No	0,154197	0,044169
Difference > 0	-0,6304	0,735089	No	0,011570	0,001597

Difference: (netěhotné_kyn_trp)-(X2trim_zrdavé_kyn__trpx)

Aspin-Welch Unequal-Variance Test Section

Alternative Hypothesis	T-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Power (Alpha=.050)	Power (Alpha=.010)
Difference <> 0	-0,5545	0,581618	No	0,084585	0,021672
Difference < 0	-0,5545	0,290809	No	0,136210	0,037052
Difference > 0	-0,5545	0,709191	No	0,014181	0,002073

Difference: (netěhotné_kyn_trp)-(X2trim_zrdavé_kyn__trpx)

Tests of Assumptions Section

Assumption	Value	Probability	Decision(.050)
Skewness Normality (netěhotné_kyn_trp)	7,0365	0,000000	Reject normality
Kurtosis Normality (netěhotné_kyn_trp)	5,7057	0,000000	Reject normality
Omnibus Normality (netěhotné_kyn_trp)	82,0679	0,000000	Reject normality
Skewness Normality (X2trim_zrdavé_kyn__trpx)		3,1817	0,001464 Reject normality
Kurtosis Normality (X2trim_zrdavé_kyn__trpx)		1,2304	0,218534 Cannot reject normality
Omnibus Normality (X2trim_zrdavé_kyn__trpx)		11,6370	0,002972 Reject normality
Variance-Ratio Equal-Variance Test	4,8289	0,000000	Reject equal variances
Modified-Levene Equal-Variance Test	0,5030	0,479804	Cannot reject equal variances

Two-Sample Test Report

Page/Date/Time 2 1.3.2024 9:47:10
 Database S:\Vyzkum\Chromed\publikace ... i moč netěhotné a těhotné.S0

Median Statistics

Variable	Count	Median	95,0% LCL of Median	95,0% UCL of Median
netěhotné_kyn_trp	42	52,97	43,32	62,1
X2trim_zrdavé_kyn__trpx	62	60,55	53,69	68,36

Mann-Whitney U or Wilcoxon Rank-Sum Test for Difference in Medians

Variable	Mann Whitney U	W Sum Ranks	Mean of W	Std Dev of W
netěhotné_kyn_trp	961	1864	2205	150,9462
X2trim_zrdavé_kyn__trpx	1643	3596	3255	150,9462

Number Sets of Ties = 2, Multiplicity Factor = 12

Alternative Hypothesis	Exact Probability		Approximation Without Correction		Approximation With Correction			
	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Z-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Z-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050
Diff<>0			-2,2591	0,023878	Yes	-2,2558	0,024085	Yes
Diff<0			-2,2591	0,011939	Yes	-2,2558	0,012043	Yes
Diff>0			-2,2591	0,988061	No	-2,2624	0,988164	No

Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test For Different Distributions

Alternative Hypothesis	Dmn Criterion Value	Reject H0 if Greater Than	Test Alpha Level	Reject H0 (Test Alpha)	Prob Level
D(1)<>D(2)	0,236559	0,2718	.050	No	0,0995
D(1)<D(2)	0,236559	0,2718	.025	No	
D(1)>D(2)	0,023810	0,2718	.025	No	

Plots Section

Two-Sample Test Report

Page/Date/Time 3 1.3.2024 9:47:10
 Database S:\Vyzkum\Chromed\publikace ... i moč netěhotné a těhotné.S0

Two-Sample Test Report

Page/Date/Time 1 1.3.2024 9:48:13
 Database S:\Vyzkum\Chromed\publikace ... i moč netěhotné a těhotné.S0

Descriptive Statistics Section

Variable	Count	Mean	Standard Deviation	Standard Error	95,0% LCL of Mean	95,0% UCL of Mean
netěhotné_kyn_trp	42	62,73024	64,33308	9,926809	42,68264	82,77784
X3trim_zrdavé_kyn__trp	62	91,65373	83,32661	32,79006	4,164342	74,9995

Note: T-alpha (netěhotné_kyn_trp) = 2,0195, T-alpha (X3trim_zrdavé_kyn__trp) = 1,9996

Confidence-Limits of Difference Section

Variance Assumption	DF	Mean Difference	Standard Deviation	Standard Error	95,0% LCL Difference	95,0% UCL Difference
Equal	102	-20,59637	48,02726	9,598072	-39,63411	-1,558645
Unequal	55,54	-20,59637	72,20757	10,76491	-42,16499	0,9722368

Note: T-alpha (Equal) = 1,9835, T-alpha (Unequal) = 2,0036

Equal-Variance T-Test Section

Alternative Hypothesis	T-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Power (Alpha=.050)	Power (Alpha=.010)
Difference <> 0	-2,1459	0,034254	Yes	0,565822	0,321053
Difference < 0	-2,1459	0,017127	Yes	0,686788	0,417260
Difference > 0	-2,1459	0,982873	No	0,000079	0,000004

Difference: (netěhotné_kyn_trp)-(X3trim_zrdavé_kyn__trp)

Aspin-Welch Unequal-Variance Test Section

Alternative Hypothesis	T-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Power (Alpha=.050)	Power (Alpha=.010)
Difference <> 0	-1,9133	0,060871	No	0,468263	0,235975
Difference < 0	-1,9133	0,030435	Yes	0,596792	0,322927
Difference > 0	-1,9133	0,969565	No	0,000204	0,000014

Difference: (netěhotné_kyn_trp)-(X3trim_zrdavé_kyn__trp)

Tests of Assumptions Section

Assumption	Value	Probability	Decision(.050)
Skewness Normality (netěhotné_kyn_trp)	7,0365	0,000000	Reject normality
Kurtosis Normality (netěhotné_kyn_trp)	5,7057	0,000000	Reject normality
Omnibus Normality (netěhotné_kyn_trp)	82,0679	0,000000	Reject normality
Skewness Normality (X3trim_zrdavé_kyn__trp)	2,4506	3,4688	0,000523 Reject normality
Kurtosis Normality (X3trim_zrdavé_kyn__trp)	18,0385	0,014261	Reject normality
Omnibus Normality (X3trim_zrdavé_kyn__trp)	3,8493	0,000121	0,000121 Reject normality
Variance-Ratio Equal-Variance Test	0,1306	0,000002	Reject equal variances
Modified-Levene Equal-Variance Test		0,718518	Cannot reject equal variances

Two-Sample Test Report

Page/Date/Time 2 1.3.2024 9:48:13
 Database S:\Vyzkum\Chromed\publikace ... i moč netěhotné a těhotné.S0

Median Statistics

Variable	Count	Median	95,0% LCL of Median	95,0% UCL of Median
netěhotné_kyn_trp	42	52,97	43,32	62,1
X3trim_zrdavé_kyn__trp	62	76,46	72,01	84,49

Mann-Whitney U or Wilcoxon Rank-Sum Test for Difference in Medians

Variable	Mann Whitney U	W Sum Ranks	Mean of W	Std Dev of W
netěhotné_kyn_trp	619	1522	2205	150,947
X3trim_zrdavé_kyn__trp	1985	3938	3255	150,947

Number Sets of Ties = 0, Multiplicity Factor = 0

Alternative Hypothesis	Exact Probability		Approximation Without Correction		Approximation With Correction			
	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Z-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Z-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050
Diff<>0			-4,5248	0,000006	Yes	-4,5215	0,000006	Yes
Diff<0			-4,5248	0,000003	Yes	-4,5215	0,000003	Yes
Diff>0			-4,5248	0,999997	No	-4,5281	0,999997	No

Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test For Different Distributions

Alternative Hypothesis	Dmn Criterion Value	Reject H0 if Greater Than	Test Alpha Level	Reject H0 (Test Alpha)	Prob Level
D(1)<>D(2)	0,478495	0,2718	.050	Yes	0,0000
D(1)<D(2)	0,478495	0,2718	.025	Yes	
D(1)>D(2)	0,023810	0,2718	.025	No	

Plots Section

Two-Sample Test Report

Page/Date/Time 3 1.3.2024 9:48:13

Database S:\Vyzkum\Chromed\publikace ... i moč netěhotné a těhotné.S0

